

Original Article

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The present study aimed to investigate the structural, morphological, elemental, optical properties and photocatalytic activity of the bare zinc oxide (ZnO) and Manganese-doped zinc oxide (Mn-ZnO) nanoparticles (NPs) using terasil blue (TB) dye as a model substrate.**Materials and Methods:** The ZnO and Mn-doped ZnO catalysts were synthesized using the co-precipitation method. The synthesized photocatalysts were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), energy dispersive X-ray (EDX), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The band energies were measured using ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) spectrophotometry.**Results:** The results obtained from XRD, EDX, SEM, and UV-Vis analyses demonstrated a successful synthesis of bare and Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles. The diffraction patterns for the synthesized ZnO and Mn-doped ZnO photocatalysts were matched with that of the standard hexagonal wurtzite structure of the standard ZnO catalyst. The average particle size for the ZnO and Mn-doped ZnO catalysts were found to be 23.46 nm and 24.38 nm, and band gap energies of 3.28eV and 3.09eV, respectively. The photocatalytic performance of the Mn-doped ZnO photocatalyst was optimized using box behnken design of response surface methodology under visible light irradiation. The operational parameters involved TB initial concentration, catalyst dosage, initial pH, and irradiation time. The optimum photodegradation efficiency of TB dye removal was achieved at 96.75% of 15mg/L of TB concentration, 0.1g/L of Mn-doped ZnO, pH = 10, and 160 minutes of irradiation time. Moreover, the photocatalytic degradation of TB over the Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles followed the pseudo-first-order kinetics model ($k = 0.0254 \text{ min}^{-1}$).**Conclusion:** Finally, the evaluation of various scavengers confirmed that the photogenerated holes and hydroxyl radicals were the major radicals for the TB photodegradation over the Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticle under visible light irradiation.

1. Introduction

The discharge of poorly treated disperse dyes enriched with several recalcitrant chemicals and carcinogenic substances into open water is a severe problem for terrestrial and aquatic life¹⁻³. Disperse dyes, which are artificial coloring agents designed for hydrophobic surfaces, find extensive application as commercial blends in the coloring of textiles. Terasil blue (TB) dye is at the forefront of dispersed dyes with C I 60767. The TB dye exhibits limited solubility in water, possesses non-ionic

characteristics, and can be employed on hydrophobic fibers through an aqueous dispersion^{4,5}. While TB dyes are predominantly utilized on polyester, they have also been applied to nylon, cellulose acetate, and acrylic fibers. However, some wet-fastness properties of the TB dye on the substrates are poor⁶. The TB dye substrate usually remains unclear and highly polluted due to the dyeing and dumping of industrial effluents directly into the ecosystem⁷.

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The removal of TB dye by the classical and conventional methods, such as adsorption, sedimentation, precipitation, and biodegradation, recorded poor success due to the generation of secondary sludge, high costs, and the need for additional planning^{8,9}. Gzar and Sabri¹⁰ studied the removal of TB dye from synthetic wastewater using low-cost agro-based adsorbents. The findings indicated that the maximum removal efficiency of TB on canocarpus was 87.5% at 50 rpm mixing speed, pH value 3, mixing time 7 hours, and the sorbent dose of 0.25g. Similarly, Jaeel¹¹ investigated the adsorption of TB on prosopis farcta, conducting a performance and modeling study. The experimental results demonstrated that the maximum removal efficiency of TB dye over PF reached 85% at a fixed 200 rpm mixing speed, pH value 8, mixing time of 90 minutes, and dose of adsorbent 0.5 g.

Heterogeneous photocatalysis has been recognized as an alternative method for the removal of pollutants, such as TB dye from the aqueous environment¹². The method, however, involves the use of hole and hydroxyl radicals significantly harvested from the light-excited photoresponsive catalyst¹³. Photoresponsive catalysts are semiconductor substances that alter the rate of chemical reactions in the presence of UV-Vis light irradiation. The common examples of photoresponsive catalysts are TiO₂, ZnO, CdO, ZrO₂, CdS, ZnS, WO₃, Fe₂O₃, CdTe, and SrTiO₂¹⁴⁻¹⁶. However, the abovementioned photocatalysts are widely used for the degradation of organic and inorganic pollutants, sensors, purification of air, and purification of soil, degradation of cancers, and microorganisms¹⁷⁻²⁰. Zinc oxide photoresponsive is a promising candidate widely used as a photocatalyst for the degradation of both organic and inorganic pollutants from the environment due to its stability, non-toxic, availability, low cost, and environmental friendliness, compared to the other photocatalysts²¹⁻²⁴. Despite its advantages, ZnO photocatalyst has limitations, including its wide band gap (3.26 eV), which restricts its absorption of ultraviolet (UV) light, and its susceptibility to photocorrosion and electron recombination processes. To overcome these drawbacks, different methods have been employed to modify band gap energy, reduce the rate of electron recombination, and shift the spectral response from UV light to visible light irradiation^{25,26}. Transition metal-dopant materials, such as Mn, Fe, Cr, and Cu, have proven effective for this purpose^{25,26}. This study chooses manganese (Mn) as the metal of interest for tuning the ZnO photoresponsive catalyst. This selection is based on the ready availability of Mn's d electrons at the t_{2g} level and their easy overlap with the valence band of the ZnO photocatalyst²⁷⁻³⁰.

Previously, the photocatalytic activity of Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles highlighted a significant success^{31,32}. Aadnan *et al.* investigated the structural, optical, and photocatalytic properties of Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles as photocatalyst for azo-dye degradation under visible light. The experimental results revealed that 96% of the azo-dye was

degraded³³. Dhanshree and Elangovan conducted a comprehensive investigation into the synthesis and characterization of ZnO and Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles, revealing noteworthy spectral responses and experimental results³⁴. In a related study, Otadi *et al.* focused on the synthesis and characterization of Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles, employing Taguchi experimental design and molecular mechanic simulation for the degradation of pyridine in a batch reactor. Their results indicated a marked improvement in the degradation of pyridine when using Mn-doped ZnO compared to undoped ZnO nanoparticles³⁵. Similarly, Khan *et al.* conducted an investigation on the production, characterization, and assessment of the biological properties of Mn-doped ZnO. The findings revealed that Mn-doped ZnO exhibited more pronounced antibacterial and antioxidant activities compared to the undoped ZnO photocatalyst³⁶.

Despite the existing body of scientific literature, research on the photocatalytic removal of TB dye over the Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles from the wastewater is scarce. Therefore, the present study aimed to investigate the structural, morphological, elemental, optical properties and photocatalytic activity of the ZnO and Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles. The photocatalytic degradation of TB dye over the synthesized Mn-ZnO nanoparticles under visible light irradiation was optimized using the Box-Behnken design (BBD) of the response surface methodology (RSM). The independent variables were the TB initial concentration, initial pH, catalyst doses, and irradiation time. In addition, the study also investigated mineralization, kinetics, reusability, and scavenger tests for the photocatalytic degradation of TB over the Mn- ZnO catalyst.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

The chemicals and reagents utilized in the study were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (United States of America) and Merck (Germany) and were of analytical grade. These reagents included zinc nitrate [Zn(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, 98% purity], manganese nitrate [Mn(NO₃)₂·4H₂O, 96% purity], sodium hydroxide [NaOH, 98% purity], dilute hydrochloric acid [HCl, 98% purity], TB dye (98% purity) and deionized water. The chemical structure of TB is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Chemical structure of terasil blue dye

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Preparation of solution

Zinc nitrate hexahydrate [$\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.07M] was prepared by dissolving 7.746g of zinc nitrate in deionized water in a 500 ml volumetric flask, with solution level brought up to the mark, and then stirring for 15 minutes. Next, a 0.07 M solution of manganese nitrate [$\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$] was provided by dissolving 3.465g of manganese nitrate in 200 ml deionized water in a measuring flask. Sodium hydroxide solution (45%) was also prepared in deionized water.

2.2.2. Synthesis of zinc oxide photocatalyst

The process reported by Hamza et al. was adopted and modified to synthesize the bare ZnO nanoparticles³⁷. Zinc nitrate (0.07M, 500 ml) was introduced into a 1000 ml beaker and stirred for 35 minutes at room temperature (28°C) using a magnetic stirrer/hot plate at the rate of 2000 rpm. Dilute sodium hydroxide (45%) was added slowly with constant stirring for 60 minutes, and the pH was adjusted to approximately 9.0 using dilute HCl or NaOH. After obtaining the desired pH (9.0), the reaction mixture was heated at 70°C with continuous stirring for 25 minutes using a magnetic stirrer at 2000 rpm. Subsequently, the mixture was left at room temperature for 2 days to facilitate precipitation, yielding white precipitates in the reaction mixture. To isolate the white ppts, the reaction mixture underwent filtration and was washed three times with 30 ml of deionized water to eliminate impurities. Thereafter, the ppts were filtered and oven-dried at 110°C for 60 minutes. The dried ppts were milled using a pestle and mortar, and then the powder was heated in the oven for 20 minutes at 110°C to remove any absorbed moisture. Then, calcination of the white powder at 300°C for 2 hours in a muffle furnace. This resulted in a white, fine powder that was cool to room temperature and thus leveled as bare ZnO nanoparticles.

2.2.3. Synthesis of mn-doped zinc oxide photocatalyst

To perform the synthesis Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles, the researchers followed a previously used method³⁶. The process involved mixing manganese nitrate and zinc nitrate solutions, and diluting sodium hydroxide (45%) to obtain the pH of 9.0. In a 1000 ml beaker, 500 ml of 0.07M zinc nitrate was gradually added to 50 ml of 0.07M manganese nitrate with continuous stirring. The reaction mixture was stirred for 25 minutes using a magnetic stirrer at the rate of 2000 rpm. In the next step, dilute sodium hydroxide was added from the burette to the reaction mixture at a 2 ml/min flow rate to reach a pH of approximately 9.0. The mixture was gently stirred in a magnetic stirrer at 1000 rpm during the pH adjustment. Following the pH adjustment, the solution underwent additional stirring with a magnetic stirrer at the rate of 1500 rpm for 60 minutes. Subsequently, the reaction

mixture was heated at 70°C for 25 minutes, and placed at room temperature for 2 days for precipitation. This process formed brown-colored precipitates in the reaction mixture. To isolate the precipitates, the reaction mixture was filtered and washed thrice with deionized water and then washed three times with 30 ml of deionized water to diminish impurities. Later, the precipitates were over-dried at 110°C for an hour and milled in a pestle and mortar. The resulting brown powdered nanoparticles underwent heating for 20 minutes at 110°C to eliminate any trace of absorbed moisture. This process yielded brown and fine powdered particles that were characterized as Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles.

2.3. Photocatalysts characterization techniques

To ascertain the crystal structure, lattice strain, crystallite size, lattice phase, chemical composition, and purity of the as-synthesized catalysts, the powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) analysis was done using Philips X pert Pro diffractometer instrument operated with a $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.54468 \text{ \AA}$) at 40 kV, 30 mA. Measurements were scanned for diffraction angle (2θ) ranging from 20-90° with a step size of 0.02° and time per step of a second. The lattice parameters consist the spacing distance between the adjacent planes in the miller indices d_{hkl} , lattice constant a, b, and c (Equations 1-4).

$$a = b = \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{3}\sin\theta_{100}} \quad (1)$$

$$c = \frac{\lambda}{\sin\theta_{001}} \quad (2)$$

$$D = \frac{k\lambda}{\beta \cos\theta} \quad (3)$$

$$SSA = \frac{6000}{D \times \rho} \quad (4)$$

2.4. Surface area of the photoresponsive catalysts

The XRD raw data were used to determine the synthesized photocatalyst's surface area (SA). The SA for the bare ZnO photocatalyst was measured using Equations 5 and 6³⁴.

$$SSA = \frac{SA}{V \times \rho} \quad (5)$$

$$S.A = SSA \times V \times \rho \quad (6)$$

2.5. Band gap measurement

The band gap energy (E_g) values for the ZnO photocatalyst were determined by analyzing the electronic data recorded for the wavelength range of 200-800 nm on the Lambda 35 Perkin Elmer UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The E_g values for the synthesized catalyst were calculated using the Schuster-Kubelka-Munk relation (Equation 7)³⁹.

$$(\alpha h\nu)^{\frac{1}{n}} = K(h\nu - E_g) \quad (7)$$

2.6. Photodegradation experiments

Photocatalytic performances of the ZnO and Mn-doped ZnO catalysts were studied for TB removal. All experiments were done in a 30 cm long, 1 Liter capacity, round bottom batch photoreactor which was maintained at 298K. The visible light source was a 300W Xenon lamp emitting at 400 nm. This lamp was jacketed in cylindrical quartz glass, dipping down the photoreactor bottom³⁸.

Typically, 500 ml aqueous solution of the desired amount of TB (10-30mg/L) and Mn-doped ZnO photocatalyst (0.01-0.06g) was added to the photoreactor, and the pH of the suspension was adjusted using 45% NaOH and HCl. This mixture was magnetically stirred for 25 minutes in the dark to establish adsorption equilibrium and then exposed to irradiation under continuous stirring at room temperature (25°C) for 180 minutes. At an interval of 20 minutes, an aliquot of 5ml was taken and filtered using a 0.45 μm cellulose nitrate filter and analyzed for residual concentration of TB at 671nm using a T60 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The percent photodegradation efficiency (D%) was estimated using Equation 8.

$$D\% = 1 - \frac{[TB]_t}{[TB]_0} \times 100 \quad (8)$$

2.7. Control experiments

Systematic control experiments for the photocatalytic TB degradation over the bare ZnO and Mn-doped ZnO catalysts under ultraviolet (UV, 96W halogen lamp) irradiation and natural sunlight illumination at optimal reaction conditions (15.00 mg/L of initial concentration, 0.05 g/L of catalysts, initial pH of 8.00, and irradiation time of 160 minutes) was conducted and compared with the photocatalysis of TB using Mn-doped ZnO photocatalyst under visible (300W Xenon lamp emitting at 400 nm) light irradiation. The power intensity of sunlight was measured by solarimeter (SL-200-KIMO) every half-hour and found to be 700Wm⁻² (the experiments were carried out in January 2023). The percentage photodegradation efficiencies were estimated using Equation 8.

2.8. Box-Benhken experimental design

The experimental design and statistical analysis were performed using the BBD of RSM because its uniqueness in generating a higher-order surface response. An experimental design was conducted at three-level-four-

variable BBD. These independent variables are the initial TB concentration (A), catalyst loading (B), initial pH (C), and irradiation time (D) operated at three levels (low, central, high) coded -1, 0, and +1 (Table 1). Other variables, including light intensity, delivery volume, agitation speed, and oxygen pressure, were maintained constant. 29 experiments (N) were done using the formula $N = 2^n + 2n + 5$. Where n is the number of variables. The % D obtained from these experiments was processed using the upgraded Design Expert software DX 13.0 to get the predicted responses, response surface, and regression model for the TB degradation.

2.9. Kinetics and mineralization profile

A series of experiments were performed at the optimal operating conditions acquired from the response surface methodology. The data obtained was tested using the integrated rate equations (Eq. 9-12) for pseudo-zero order, pseudo-first-order, pseudo-second order kinetics model, and half-life for pseudo-first-order scheme.

$$\frac{[TB]_0}{[TB]_t} = -k t \quad (9)$$

$$\ln \frac{[TB]_0}{[TB]_t} = k_{app} t \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{1}{[TB]_t} - \frac{1}{[TB]_0} = k t \quad (11) \text{ and}$$

$$t_{1/2} = \frac{0.693}{k} \quad (12)$$

Where, $[TB]_0$ and $[TB]_t$ define the initial and final concentration of TB, t serves as the irradiation time, k and k_{app} are the rate constant and apparent rate constant, respectively, and $t_{1/2}$ denotes the half-life for pseudo-first-order reactions. The basic kinetic parameter (k) was calculated from the plot of $\frac{[TB]_0}{[TB]_t}$ against t for pseudo-zero order kinetics. Similarly, a plot of $\ln \frac{[TB]_0}{[TB]_t}$ versus t gives a linear graph that passes through the origin and the apparent rate constant, k_{app} (min⁻¹) was estimated from the slope. While the plot of $\frac{1}{[TB]_t}$ against t also gave a linear graph passing through the intercept in which the TB initial concentration was calculated from the intersection and rate constant (k) from the slope. The half-life for the photocatalytic degradation of TB over the synthesized photocatalysts was calculated at optimal conditions.

The progress of the mineralization process was monitored by measuring total organic carbon (TOC) using a Shimadzu 00087 TOC analyzer. The extent of mineralization of TB dye was calculated using Eq. 13.

Table 1. The level factorial Box-Benhken design

Variable	Notation	Levels (Codes)		
Initial TB concentration (mg/L)	A	10(-1)	15(0)	20(+1)
Catalyst loading (g/L)	B	0.01(-1)	0.05(0)	0.10(+1)
Initial pH	C	4(-1)	8(0)	12(+1)
Irradiation time (min)	D	20(-1)	80(0)	180(+1)

TB: Terasil blue

Figure 2. Activity of different amounts of manganese doses in the degradation of TB

$$\% \text{ mineralization} = 1 - \frac{[TOC]_t}{[TOC]_0} \times 100 \quad (13)$$

$[TOC]_0$ is the total organic carbon before mineralization and $[TOC]_t$ is the total organic carbon at a given time t .

2.10. Radical scavenger experiments

The primary reactive radicals and holes were detected through radical scavenging experiments to investigate the significant role of reactive radicals generated during the photocatalytic removal of TB over Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles. During the photocatalytic process, the holes (h^+), hydroxyl radical ($\bullet OH$), and superoxide radical ($\bullet O_2^-$) are trapped by adding ammonium oxalate (AO), (h^+ scavenger), t -butanol ($\bullet OH$ scavenger), and p -benzoquinone ($\bullet O_2^-$ scavenger) into the reaction solution respectively. Typically, 10.00mg of Mn-ZnO and 10.00mM of radical scavengers were introduced into 10.00 mg/L of TB solution. Then, the suspension was irradiated using the 300W Xenon lamp emitting at 400nm simultaneously. Finally, the TB photodegradation efficiencies were calculated using Eq. (8).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Preliminary studies

The photoactivity of different amounts of manganese

dopant in removing TB dye was monitored using 15.00 mgL^{-1} solution of TB, 0.05 gL^{-1} ZnO catalysts with Mn content in the 2 to 16 % (Figure 2). The observed trend revealed the relationship between the photocatalytic degradation efficiency of TB and the carbon content, indicating an increase from 2% to 7%. However, beyond 7% manganese, there was a consistent decline in degradation efficiency. Thus, 7 % Mn-doped ZnO was found to be the optimal (98%) amount of dopant when compared to the rest of the Mn-doped ZnO photocatalysts. The enhanced photocatalytic activity of the 7 wt% Mn-doped ZnO may be attributed to the creation of just enough shallow trapping sites for the charge carriers by the presence of Mn, which causes a difference in the surface arrival time of electron and hole pairs and prevents recombination⁴⁰.

3.2. Spectral results

3.2.1. Structural properties

Figure 3 displays the powder X-ray diffraction patterns for the U-doped ZnO and Mn-doped ZnO catalysts. As indicated, the reflection peaks at 2θ values of 31.8°, 34.4°, 36.3°, 47.6°, 56.7°, 62.9°, 66.5°, 68.0° and 69.1° corresponded to the structural miller indices (100), (002), (101), (102), (110), (103), (200), (112), and (201) of U- ZnO catalyst. Similarly, the diffraction peaks observed at $2\theta = 31.7^\circ$, 34.4°, 36.2°, 47.6°, 56.6°, 62.8°, 66.4°, 67.9°, and 69.0° corresponded to the (100), (002), (101), (102), (110),

Figure 3. The X-ray diffraction patterns of photocatalysts. a: Undoped ZnO, b: Mn-doped ZnO

Table 2. The lattice parameters and crystal structure of undoped and Mn-doped ZnO catalysts

Photoresponsive Catalyst	$d_{100}(\text{\AA})$	Lattice parameters in (\AA)		Crystal structure	Volume of a unit cell (\AA)	Unit cells per particle
		a = b	c			
ZnO	2.9216	3.2476	5.2031	Hexagonal wurtzite	47.4939	1.2868
Mn-doped ZnO	2.9136	3.2495	5.2040	Hexagonal wurtzite	47.5869	1.9721

ZnO: Zinc oxide, Mn-doped ZnO: Manganese-doped zinc oxide

(103), (200), (112), and (201) reflection planes of the Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles (Figure 3b). The absence of impurity peaks is a primary manifestation of a single phase, low content of accommodated dopant, and high purity of the synthesized photocatalysts⁴¹.

The obtained XRD patterns for the ZnO and the Mn-doped ZnO matched the standard hexagonal wurtzite structure of ZnO catalyst (JCPDS 01-080-9087). As can be seen in Table 2, The unit cell parameters calculated based on ZnO lattice planes (101) and (102) aligned with the standard lattice parameters ($a = 3.2465\text{\AA}$ and $c = 5.2030\text{\AA}$; JCPDS Card no; 070-7036) and ($a = 3.2494\text{\AA}$ and $c = 5.2038\text{\AA}$; JCPDS Card no; 01-087-7523, respectively). The values calculated showed slight increases in the unit cell parameters, including the spacing distance and unit cell volume (Table 2).

The high crystallinity of the as-prepared ZnO powders is indicated by the outstanding sharpness of diffraction peaks⁴². Upon doping, the specific surface area of the Mn-doped ZnO increased from 45.78 to 58.27 (m^2g^{-1}) while the XRD-based particle size slightly increased from 23.46 to 24.38 nm (Table 3). These findings are in line with the previous report³². Moreover, an increase in the surface area of Mn-doped ZnO photocatalysts has usually been linked to enhanced interfacial reactions⁴³.

3.2.2. Morphological properties

The surface morphology of the as-prepared bare ZnO and Mn-doped ZnO is shown in Figure 4. The aggregation

of particles is seen in the U- ZnO nanoparticles (Figure 4a), and agglomeration of the particles was pronounced for the Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles (Figure 4b). This might be due to the addition of dopant (Mn) during the synthesis⁴⁴. These results are consistent with the previous report⁴⁵. Therefore, Figure 4 reveals the surface morphology of synthesized photocatalysts.

3.2.3 Elemental properties

The presence of the Mn atom with Zn and O atoms in the nanoparticles is substantiated by EDX analysis. Figure 5 illustrates the EDX spectra of bare ZnO and 7% Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles (the optimal catalyst). Figure 5a demonstrates that the spectra consist of Zinc (Zn) and oxygen (O) atoms only, while Figure 5b shows the presence of Zinc (Zn), oxygen (O) and manganese (Mn) atoms. These results provide concrete evidence of the successful synthesis of both U-ZnO and Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles, emphasizing the high purity of the sample synthesized. These findings are consistent with the previous report^{36,46}.

The weight and atomic percent composition of Zn and O atoms for (a) U-ZnO and Zn, O, and Mn atoms in the Mn-doped ZnO are shown in Table 4. Despite ZnO generally being considered an n-type semiconductor with predominant defects like interstitial zinc and oxygen vacancies, the current results showed zinc and oxygen excess deficiency. This implies the existence of interstitial oxygen and the less observed p-type semiconducting ZnO nanoparticles⁴⁷.

Table 3. The size, surface area, and band gap of the ZnO Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles

Photocatalyst	D(nm)	Specific surface area (m^2g^{-1})	Band gap (eV)
U- ZnO	23.46	45.78	3.28
Mn-doped ZnO	24.38	58.27	3.09

D: Average crystallite size

Figure 4. The SEM Micrographs of (a) Undoped ZnO and (b) Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles.

Figure 5. The EDX spectra (a) undoped ZnO and (b) Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles

Table 4. Weight and Atomic percentage of the constituents of undoped and Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles

Element	U- ZnO nanoparticles		Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles	
	Wt%	At%	Wt%	At%
Mn K	-	-	4.94	3.80
O K	18.99	50.51	23.03	53.56
Zn L	81.01	50.49	72.03	42.64
Total	100 %		100 %	

U-ZnO: Undoped zinc oxide, Wt%: Weight percentage, At%: Atomic percentage, Mn-doped ZnO: Manganese doped zinc oxide, Mn K: Manganese K-shell, O K: Oxygen K-shell, Zn L: Zinc L-shell

3.2.4 Optical properties

The band gap energies of the obtained ZnO nanoparticles were measured from the absorption data using Kubelka-Munk's intercept of the plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ against $h\nu$ (Figure 6). The figure shows linearity in the vicinity of the band gap region for both the Mn-doped ZnO and that of the bare ZnO, revealing that the Mn-doping did not change the direct electron transition characteristics of the ZnO³⁶. The band gap energy values for the undoped and Mn-doped ZnO photocatalysts were 3.28eV and 3.09 eV, respectively, confirming the ability of the former to absorb more visible light relatively. In other words, Mn doping reduces the band gap energy of the bared ZnO catalyst due to decreased particle size and adsorption capacity between the Mn-doped ZnO and pollutant, which further contributes to the charge-transfer process easily⁴⁸. The observed ease of charge transitions suggests that Mn-doped ZnO exhibits higher conductivity compared to bare ZnO catalyst. Consequently, Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles demonstrate

excellent conductivity, making them suitable for applications as electrocatalysts in photoelectrochemical reactions⁴⁹.

Figure 6. Band gap plots for the ZnO powders. U-ZnO (a) Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles (b)

Table 5. Results of Box-Behnken design with experimental and predicted degradation efficiencies

Run	Experimental efficiencies (%D _{exp})	Predicted efficiencies (%D _{pred})
1	67.00	71.88
2	89.00	87.04
3	87.00	93.54
4	78.00	77.71
5	73.00	87.71
6	97.00	89.21
7	79.00	91.38
8	98.00	87.88
9	92.00	94.63
10	78.00	82.79
11	87.00	84.29
12	96.00	95.46
13	96.00	90.96
14	91.00	74.63
15	49.00	67.46
16	96.75	96.65
17	94.00	88.83
18	80.00	79.50
19	85.00	78.83
20	89.00	87.50
21	93.00	81.00
22	96.00	93.67
23	93.00	88.67
24	83.00	88.33
25	94.00	88.40
26	90.40	88.40
27	91.00	88.40
28	80.00	88.40
29	87.00	88.40

3.3. Experimental results and process optimization

3.3.1 Statistical analysis

A total of 29 runs of BBD were conducted. The TB degradation efficiencies of the various photoexperiments (%D_{exp}) and the corresponding statistically predicted values ((%D_{pred}) are shown in Table 5. The experimental optimum photoremoval efficiency (96.75%) was achieved at A-initial concentration of TB (15.00 mgL⁻¹), B-catalyst doses (0.1gL⁻¹), C-pH (10), and D-irradiation time (160 minutes).

Table 5 demonstrates that the experimental and predicted photodegradation efficiencies are in good correlation, as attested by the linear correlation of normal probabilities plot of residuals (Figure 7). Most of the normal probability plot points lied roughly in a straight line.

Table 6. Analysis of variance for the quadratic model

Source	Sum of square	df	Mean Square	F value	P value	Remarks
Model	6546.54	6	6543.00	13.89	0.0001	significance
A	5671.32	1	5671.32	88.65	<0.0001	
B	345.34	1	345.34	6.75	0.0012	
C	145.21	1	145.21	7.11	0.0014	
A ²	134.21	1	134.21	12.22	0.0073	
B ²	543.11	1	543.11	14.62	0.0092	
C ²	1145.34	1	1145.34	13.11	0.9870	
Residual	1237.32	22	58.12			
Lack of fit	876.76	18	77.78	0.62	0.7621	not significant
Pure Error	345.11	4	72.14			
Cor. Total	897.58	28				

df: Degree of freedom

Figure 7. Linear normal plot of residual

The removal model was of a reduced quadratic type, as indicated by Equation 14, due to the absence of support from the irradiation time term (D), cross terms (AB, AC, AD, BC, BD, CD), and the square term (D²) in the model hierarchy.

$$D\% = +80.73 + 1.28A - 1.98B + 0.98C + 2.22A^2 - 0.20B^2 - 0.98C^2 \quad (14)$$

Table 6 shows the results of ANOVA for the reduced quadratic model applicable to this study. As can be seen, the F-values of the model and the model terms A, B, C, A², B², and C² were > 4, indicating low chances of noise and confirming the significance of the quadratic model. This is further corroborated by the values of Prob > F, which are all < 0.05 less. The quality of the developed model was high, given that R² = 0.9815. This implies that the independent variables within the studied range explained 96.75 % of the variations for the removal of TB dye. The lack of fit value of 0.62 was insignificant compared to the pure error with the p-value of 0.7621 > 0.05, indicating the model predictability. Meanwhile, the small p-value (below 0.0001) confirmed the significance of the model term. Therefore, the significant terms among the tested process parameters were solution pH > TB concentration > second order of solution pH > second order of Mn-ZnO photocatalyst dosage > Mn-ZnO photocatalysts dosage > second order of TB concentration. Other model terms were insignificant, as their p-values were above 0.1000.

As indicated in Table 7, the coefficient of variance (CV = 1.14) was low, indicating high precision and good reliability of the experimental values. Adequate precision

Table 7. Analysis of variance results for the quadratic model

Parameter	Value
Standard deviation	3.01
Mean	82.72
Coefficient of variance (CV,%)	1.14
Coefficient of determination (R ²)	0.979
Adjusted R ²	0.969
Predicted R ²	0.798
Adequate precision	33.17

measure of 33.17, which was well above 4, revealed an adequate signal. The regression model demonstrated a good relationship between independent variables, as both R² (0.988) was close to 1. The p values of the major parameters (A and C) influencing the percentage removal of TB were significant ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, the quadratic terms (A² and B²) had a probability of less than 0.05, revealing a significant contribution to TB degradation.

In order to validate the reduced quadratic model obtained in this study, individual runs were conducted at low, middle, and high levels, and the obtained results were compared to the predicted values (Table 8). The experimental results were very close to the predicted values (96.66 %), confirming the reliability of the BBD.

3.3.2. 3D Response surface plot analysis

Figure 8 indicates the response surface plots showing the effect of operating parameters. Figure 8a indicates the three-dimensional response surface of the influence of Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles and initial TB concentration at constant initial pH and irradiation time. The degradation percentage enhanced proportionally with the enhancement of Mn-doped ZnO catalyst due to enhancement in the generation of hydroxyl radicals. Higher catalyst loading was antagonistic to the degradation process due to the reduced catalyst surface area available for light absorption and TB adsorption. Figure 8b shows the effect of TB initial concentration and initial pH solution in removing TB dye.

Table 8. Validation data for the analysis of variance

Run	Initial terasil blue concentration (mg/L)	Catalyst loading (g/L ⁻¹)	Initial pH	Experimental efficiency (%)	Predicted efficiency (%)
1	10.00	0.01	4.00	77.46 ± 0.45	77.01
2	15.00	0.05	8.00	96.46 ± 0.03	96.66
3	20.00	0.1	12.00	71.69 ± 0.35	71.34

Figure 8. Response surface plots showing the interaction of initial terasil blue concentration with (a) catalyst dosage (b) initial pH (c) Irradiation time

However, the degradation efficiency decreased with enhancing TB concentration ascribed to the interception of the photon before they reach the surface of the Mn-ZnO photocatalyst. Furthermore, the Columbia repulsion between the negatively charged Mn-doped ZnO photocatalyst surface and hydroxyl anions at highly alkaline conditions reduced the TB removal rate by suppressing the generation of hydroxyl radicals. Figure 8c demonstrates the interaction between the initial TB concentration and irradiation time at constant pH and catalyst doses. However, the removal efficiency increased with increasing irradiation time and decreasing TB initial concentration. On the other hand, the percentage photo removal decreased with decreasing irradiation time and increasing TB initial concentration.

3.4 Evaluation of photocatalytic activity of optimized Mn-ZnO nanoparticle

In order to determine the implication of the photocatalytic degradation of TB over the optimized Mn-ZnO nanoparticles under visible light irradiation, two control experiments were conducted under two different experimental conditions. The first was performed under UV; the second was under natural sunlight at optimal reaction variables (15.00 mg/L TB initial concentration, 0.1 g/L of Mn-ZnO, initial pH of 10, and irradiation time of 160 minutes). The results are illustrated in Figures 9-11. From Figure 9, the photocatalytic removal of TB over bare ZnO and Mn-doped ZnO catalysts under visible light resulted in percentage removals of 96.88% and 81.00%, respectively. This clear disparity indicates that the Mn-doped ZnO photocatalyst, as synthesized, exhibits superior photodegradation efficiency for TB removal compared to the pure ZnO photocatalyst. The heightened photocatalytic activity of Mn-doped ZnO can be attributed to potential penetration and enhanced stimulation of nanoparticles by visible light^{29,30}.

Figure 9. Effect of irradiation time on the photocatalytic degradation of terasil blue under visible light irradiation ZnO (a) Mn-doped ZnO (b)

Concurrently, the percentage removal of TB by photocatalysis over the pure ZnO and Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles under UV light was 92.50 % and 80.00 %, respectively (Figure 10). This indicates that the as-synthesized ZnO photocatalyst has a better photodegradation efficiency for removing TB than the Mn-doped ZnO catalyst. The high photocatalytic activity of the ZnO can be attributed to its wide band gap, possible penetration, and high stimulation of nanoparticles by UV light^{29, 53}.

Similarly, TB removal rates of by photocatalysis over the undoped ZnO and Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles under natural light were 86.90 % and 74.50 %, respectively, indicating better photoefficiency of the synthesized ZnO photocatalyst for TB removal (Figure 11). The high photocatalytic activity of the ZnO can be attributed to its wide band gap, possible penetration, and high stimulation of nanoparticles by the natural sunlight⁵³

The results presented in Figures 9, 10, and 11, depicting the photocatalytic degradation of TB dye over synthesized ZnO and Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles under various experimental conditions, clearly elucidate that the TB removal rate of 96.88% achieved over the optimized Mn-doped ZnO under visible light irradiation is significantly superior to the degradation of TB over ZnO. This is due to the low band gap and reduced rate of the

Figure 10. Effect of irradiation time on the photocatalytic degradation of terasil blue under UV light irradiation Mn- ZnO (a) ZnO(b)

Figure 11. Effect of irradiation time on the photocatalytic degradation of terasil blue under natural sunlight irradiation Mn- ZnO (a) ZnO(b)

electron recombination process. Thus, the optimized Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles could be used for the treatment of wastewater as well as other pollutants such as pesticides, herbicides, microorganisms (bacteria, viruses), purification of air, self-cleaning, treatment of trace metals and artificial photosynthesis^{25, 35, 36}. Furthermore, the present study can also be applied in the textiles, papers, ceramics, plastics, rubbers, and pharmaceutical industries to treat their effluents^{29,30, 53}. In addition, the optimized Mn-doped ZnO catalyst can also be used in other fields of science and technology for different purposes²⁵. For instance, in electrochemistry, the Mn-ZnO catalyst could be used as a good conductor because of the transition of electrons between the valence band and conduction band⁵³. In biotechnology, the optimized Mn-ZnO catalyst could produce biofuel and biodiesel²⁹. Similarly, in health, this study can be used to treat cancer cells from the patient^{25,36}. Thus, the optimized Mn-doped ZnO catalyst could be practically applied to treat wastewater and other relevant areas, as stated before.

3.5. Reusability study

To consider the reusability of the Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles, a systematic experiment was done at the optimum conditions of the photocatalytic removal of TB over the Mn-doped ZnO. Residual catalyst from the degradation experiment was filtered, washed, dried, and then recycled in the fresh experiment (Figure 12).

The observations from Figure 12 reveal a steady decrease in the degradation of TB during the first and second cycles, but from cycles 3 to 7, the degradation remains consistent. This pattern illustrates the stability and effectiveness of the Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles in TB degradation.

3.6. Photocatalytic mechanism

During TB photocatalytic removal of dye over the Mn-

Figure 12. Reusability of Mn-doped ZnO in the degradation of terasil blue dye

doped ZnO nanoparticles, the h^+ , $\bullet OH$, and $\bullet O_2^-$ are eliminated by adding AO (h^+ scavenger)⁵⁰, *t*-BuOH ($\bullet OH$ scavenger)⁵¹, and *p*-BQ ($\bullet O_2^-$ scavenger)⁵² into the reaction solution respectively and the result is presented in Figure 13.

Figure 10 indicate that adding *p*-BuOH and AO could slightly change TB photocatalytic removal, while a significant change was observed with the addition of *p*-BQ scavenger. These show that the decrease of the photocatalytic removal in the presence of scavengers presents benzo-quinonine > ammonium oxalate > tertiary-

butanol. So, the hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet OH$) are the main reactive species during the photocatalytic removal of TB under visible light irradiation.

3.7. Mineralization and kinetics study

Mineralization is among the most desirable parameters in the degradation of TB dye over the Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles. In the current study, mineralization was monitored based on total organic carbon (TOC) measurement (Figure 14).

Figure 13. Degradation efficiency of terasil blue in the absence and presence of scavengers

Figure 14. Variation of terasil blue mineralization with time at optimized conditions

Figure 15. Pseudo-first-order plot of degradation of terasil blue over the Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles

Table 9. Kinetic parameters for the degradation of terasil blue over the Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles

S/N	Schemes	Apparent rate constant (k_{app}), min^{-1}	Regression model (R^2) value	Half-life ($t_{1/2}$) min^{-1}
1.0	Pseudo-zero-order	0.0236	0.9239	1.569
2.0	Pseudo-first-order	0.0254	0.9929	1.658
3.0	Pseudo-second-order	0.0124	0.8999	1.763

S/N: Serial number

The mineralization of TB dye increased steadily with an irradiation time up to 78%. However, the photocatalytic degradation of TB over the Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles was evaluated using pseudo-zero-order (Equation 9), pseudo-first-order (Equation 10), and pseudo-second-order (Equation 11) kinetic schemes, and the results are illustrated in Figure 15. As can be seen, the process agreed with pseudo-first-order model ($R^2 = 0.9929$) with an apparent rate constant (k_{app}) of 0.0254 min^{-1} . The rate constant corresponding to each equation was obtained from the slope. The rate constant (k) and half-life ($t_{1/2}$) obtained in this study are presented in Table 9.

4. Conclusion

The photoresponsive Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles were prepared using the co-precipitation method. The obtained nanoparticles were characterized using XRD, SEM, EDX techniques. The UV-Vis spectrophotometry was employed to determine the structural, morphological, and elemental properties, as well as band gap values. Based on the XRD, SEM, and UV-Vis analyses, the synthesized Mn-doped ZnO photocatalyst was matched with that of the hexagonal wurtzite structure. The particle size, specific surface area, and band gap values were found to be 24.38nm, $58.27 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, and 3.09eV, respectively. The optimum degradation efficiency of 96.75% was achieved at 15.00mg/L of TB, 0.10g/L of Mn-doped ZnO catalyst, initial pH of 10.00, and 160 minutes of irradiation. Finally, the photodegradation of TB dye over the Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles fit pseudo-first-order kinetics with the apparent rate constant (k_{app}) of 0.0254 min^{-1} .

Declarations

Competing interests

There was no conflict of interest between the authors of this work.

Authors' contribution

All authors participated in data collection, preparation of the manuscript, interpretation of results, review, and preparation of the revised manuscript.

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Ethical considerations

The authors checked the plagiarism and consented to the publishing of the article. The authors have also checked the article fabrication, double publication and redundancy.

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